

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 4.3 to AD4.1 – Blood Sampling Questionnaire for Teenagers (12 – 17 years)

WP 4

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Technical reference

Work package	WP4 - Monitoring and Exposure
Task	T 4.1 - Human Biomonitoring S4.1.1.1 - Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct
Dissemination level ¹	VITO/ISCIH
Lead Beneficiary/ Responsible AE	SpF
Co-authors	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be ;
Contributing Participants	Maria Torres Toda (LNS, Luxembourg); Andromachi Katsonouri (MOH-CY, Cyprus), Katherine Gabriel (AUTH, Greece); Annelies De Decker (PIH, Belgium); Elly DEN HOND (PIH, Belgium); Anskje VAN MENSEL (PIH, Belgium); Jurgen Buekers (VITO, Belgium); Eva Govarts (VITO, Belgium)
Deliverables	30 June 2023
Actual submission date	22 June 2023

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
Version 1	2023-06-22	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	
Version 2	2023-07-11	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after external review of AD4.1
Version 3	2023-09-18	Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after GS partners' review of the questionnaires

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Table of Contents

Technical reference _____	7
Document history _____	8
Table of Contents _____	10
B.01: Question for fieldworker about blood sample collection _____	11
I.00: Questionnaire information _____	12
B.02: Question for participant about blood sample collection _____	12
UB.03: Recent exposure _____	12

B.01: Question for fieldworker about blood sample collection

Q130: Has the blood sample been taken?

Yes

No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q130.1: Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the blood sample

Unsuccessful puncture

No consent

Sampling was spontaneously refused

Other reason

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q130.1.1: Other reason, that being _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q131: When was the blood sample obtained? **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1: On **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.2: At **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q131.2.1: Hour _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q131.2.2: Minute _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q133: What total amount was sampled? _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q133.1: Please specify which tubes **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q133.1.1: Plastic serum vacutainer 4ml

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q133.1.2: Glass serum vacutainer 5ml

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q133.1.3: Edta vacutainer 6ml

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q134: If the gross volume was taken in sub-samples: how many sub-samples were taken? **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.1: Small tubes **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.1.1: Amount _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.1.2: Volume taken in each sub-sample _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.2: Large tubes **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.2.1: Amount _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.2.2: Volume taken in each sub-sample _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q135: Is there a sampling label on the container?

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q136: Is there a label with the correct participant id on the container?

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q137: Were there any peculiarities with the sample or participant's answers?

No

Yes

Refused to provide sample

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q137.1: Which ones? _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

I.00: Questionnaire information

Q093: Id (participant) _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q094: Id (interviewer) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q095: Date of the interview **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q098: Interview place / interview platform _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

B.02: Question for participant about blood sample collection

Q132: When was your child's last meal before blood sample collection? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1: On **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1.1: Day _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1.2: Month _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1.3: Year _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.2: At **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.2.1: Hour _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.2.2: Minute _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

UB.03: Recent exposure

Q138: Before providing the sample, when did your child last eat any food belonging to the following food groups?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.1: White fish (e.G. Hake, snapper, sea bream, cod, haddock, grouper, halibut, tilapia, bass)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.2: Small oily fish (e.G. Anchovy, sardines, salmon)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

ANNEX 4.3 – BLOOD SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.3: Big oily fish (e.G. Sword fish, tuna, school shark)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.4: Other seafood (e.G. Octopus, squid, shrimps, scampi)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.5: Meat (e.G. White and red meat, game, offal)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.6: Snails

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.7: Rice

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.8: Other cereals (e.G. Bread, crackers, grains, pasta)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.9: Algae/seaweeds

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.10: Mushrooms

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.11: Vegetables (e.G. Potatoes, leafy vegetables)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.12: Fruits (e.G. Oranges, grapes, apples)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.13: Dairy products (e.G. Butter, milk, cheese)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.14: Fats (animal, e.G. Lard and vegetal, e.G. Olive or sunflower oil)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.15: Potato chips (packaged)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.16: Microwave popcorn (cooked in bags)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 4.3 – BLOOD SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q138.18: Peanuts

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.19: Chewing gum

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.20: Smoked food (e.G. Ham, smoked pork, smoked cheese, frankfurters)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.21: Canned food

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.22: Fast food

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.23: Ready meals (in plastic packaging)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q139: When did your child last take dietary supplements (algae, spirulina, vitamins, minerals, omega-3 fatty acids etc...) during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Not at all
- Less than 5 hours ago
- Between 5 and 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q139.1: If yes, please specify supplement _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q140: Before providing the sample, when did your child last drink any beverages belonging to the following list?

ANNEX 4.3 – BLOOD SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.1: Barley coffee

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.3: Whole milk

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.4: Vegetable/fruit juice (hand-made)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.5: Vegetable/fruit juice (processed)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.6: Beer

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.7: Red wine

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.8: Japanese rice wine 'sake'

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q140.9: Tea or any other drink prepared in metal recipient (e.G. Arabic teapot)

ANNEX 4.3 – BLOOD SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q141: Has your child been exposed to tobacco smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes, i have smoked
- Yes, i have been exposed to second hand smoke (passive smoking)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q141.1: How many cigarettes and other smoking products did you smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11 or more
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q141.2: How long has your child been exposed to secondhand smoking during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Less than an hour
- More than 1 hour
- More than 4 hours
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q142: Has your child been exposed to electronic cigarettes vapors during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes, i have vaped
- Yes, i have been exposed to secondhand vape smoke

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q142.1: How many puffs of e-cigarettes did you take during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11 or more
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q142.2: How long has your child been exposed to secondhand vape smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Less than an hour
- More than 1 hour
- More than 4 hours
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q143: Have you used any smokeless tobacco products such as snuff/snus, dip, or chewing tobacco during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q143.1: How many loadings did you take during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6 or more
- Don't know

ANNEX 4.3 – BLOOD SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q144: Did your child take any medicines during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

No

Yes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q144.1: If yes, please specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q145: During the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did your child undergo one or more of the following medical treatments? Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q145.1: Intravenous (iv) infusion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q145.2: Donated blood **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q145.3: Dialysis **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q145.4: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**